

The Impact of Live Webcast Product Recommendation on Consumers' Purchase Intention

Chen Weibin

Abstract

In 2012, China's mobile phone users surpassed desktop computers to become the largest Internet terminal, thus irreversibly entering the mobile Internet era. The marketing work of enterprises also appeared a new inflexion point, from the marketing of the industrial economy and information economy to the marketing of the mobile Internet era. In 2021, the total number of mobile Internet users in China exceeded 1.6 billion, and mobile social platform users reached 1 billion. With this, the price of user growth was significantly low, the bonus of traffic growth gradually disappeared, and the stock era has come. It means that enterprises need to change their business ideas and marketing strategies. Operating stock users primarily rely on community interaction and the establishment and maintenance of community emotion in the mobile Internet environment. The success of community operation is the critical factor as the opinion leader of organizers and influencers. The group of mobile Internet opinion leaders is gradually increasing, and professional opinion leaders also appear. This paper studies the impact on consumers' purchase intention from the perspective of information presentation of opinion leaders' commodity recommendation in the mobile network community, enriches the knowledge system of the relationship between opinion leaders and consumers' purchase intention in the mobile Internet environment and has practical significance for the marketing of current enterprises and individuals engaged in business activities.

Keywords: *Opinion leader, Information presentation, Perceived value, Relationship strength, Purchase intention.*

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About Author (s)

Chen Weibin, Asia Metropolitan University, Malaysia.

1. INTRODUCTION

According to the China Internet development report 2021, as of June 2021, the number of Internet users in China has reached 1.011 billion, and the Internet penetration rate has reached 71.6%. Digital technology has been integrated into social exchanges and daily life, such as education and medical treatment. In particular, the total number of mobile Internet users exceeds 1.6 billion; The number of 5g network users exceeds 160 million, and the total number of 5g base stations in China has reached 961000, accounting for more than 70% of the world, realizing the full coverage of all cities above prefecture level. AI media consulting's Research Report on China's mobile social industry in the first half of 2021 points out that the scale of China's mobile social users has reached 924 million in 2020, and it is expected that the overall number of China's mobile social users will exceed 1 billion in 2022. AI media consulting analysts believe that with the advent of the 5g era, based on the original users, the innovation of China's mobile social platform products will further release social value. According to the data released by the media team of GF Securities, WeChat users, China's most powerful social software, use WeChat for an average of 90 minutes a day. Community interaction accounts for 30% of the 38 billion daily message interactions on WeChat. The services provided to users through communities such as a circle of friends and WeChat groups can take up many users' time. From the attention economy perspective, competing for user time is the critical factor of business competition. There are substantial business opportunities where users pay attention and spend their time. Since the birth of WeChat, enterprises and individuals have worked from WeChat official account, subscription number, enterprise WeChat, WeChat friends circle, WeChat group, etc. However, there are specific effects in the early stage. With the geometric growth of the above information content, the audience gradually shows audio-visual fatigue and declines in interest. For enterprises and individuals engaged in business activities, the massive traffic of WeChat conflicts with user stickiness and user needs, but the gap between consumer needs and the content presented in reality is a new opportunity for enterprises and individuals. At the same time, with the increasing use of mobile social media, the time and space of brand marketing communication have a more significant impact on marketing and play an important role. Communication has entered a new era with the leap from traditional media to new media. At present, China's top five Internet community active platforms are WeChat group, QQ group, WeChat official account, self-built website APP and micro-blog. The social and commercial value of mobile Internet media is enormous. It is an indispensable tool for businesses and individuals to maintain business activities. This study focuses on the impact of social media opinion leaders' product recommendation information on consumers' purchase intention in the mobile Internet environment. This study involves disciplines, theories, and models such as word-of-mouth marketing, marketing communication, social psychology, consumer behaviour, SOR model, mobile internet marketing, perceived value, social presence, etc. The purpose of this study is to analyze and study the influence mechanism of mobile social media community opinion leaders' recommendation of merchant commodity information and consumer purchase behaviour to provide a reference for enterprises in mobile internet marketing.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Preliminary research

(1) Consumers' Purchase Intention

The international organization for standardization believes that consumers are individual members of society who purchase and use goods and services for personal consumption. Will is the premise of behaviour activities. Only when individuals have will can they take some behaviour activities. Individual will determines behaviour. The term intention was initially a psychological concept. Consumers' purchase intention changes their psychological state and

responses when they receive some information or stimulation. Mu Weisong (2006) believes that purchase intention is the subjective possibility of consumers' purchase behaviour and the prelude to purchase decisions. Cheng Zhenyu (2013) believes that in e-commerce, purchase intention is the possibility for consumers to purchase goods or services on social platforms through the Internet and terminal devices.

(2) Relationship Strength

Brown (1987) defined relationship strength as the familiarity between the information source and the information receiver. Frenzen and Davis (1990) believe that relationship strength is multidimensional, including intimacy, support, relevance and closeness. Brown and others believe that relationship strength is the natural relationship between customers and others from strong and primary to weak and secondary.

(3) Perceived Value

Lu Xiongwen's definition of perceived value in the dictionary of management is that customer perceived value is the subjective evaluation of the utility of products or services after customers perceive the benefits of products or services and subtract the cost they pay when obtaining products or services. It reflects customers' specific cognition of the value of products or services, which is different from the objective value of products or services in the general sense. Customer perceived value is considered the result of the subjective cognition of customer assigned value. Zeithaml (1988) believes that consumers' perceived value comes from obtaining products or services. It is the overall evaluation after consumers weigh the perceived benefits and costs of the consumption process.

Figure 2-1 Perceived Value Model

(4) Information Quality of Mobile Internet Media

McLuhan's (1964) view on media extends the human body. Media is information. His famous sentence "media is information" shaped the basic cognition of media for the contemporary. The information quality of this study refers to the beauty, professionalism, richness, authenticity, effectiveness and timeliness of the product information recommended by users. Specific forms of information quality:

- i. From the perspective of communication, information quality can be an expression package, a paragraph of text, a poster and a short video.
- ii. From the perspective of products, information quality can be the concept, function, use-value and user purchase reason.
- iii. From users' perspective, information quality can be an experience, greeting and service.

iv. From the perspective of enterprises, information quality can be a theory, reputation and culture.

(5) Objective Expression and Intentional Expression

Bao Ruixue (2019) believes that objective expression means that opinion leaders are objective and calm when disseminating product information and do not express their subjective attitude towards products. On the other hand, the intentional expression means that opinion leaders have subjective emotions and express a positive attitude towards products when disseminating product information. The definition of objective expression adopted in this study refers to that opinion leaders state the facts they receive and describe the natural attributes of commodity information itself. On the other hand, the definition of intention expression adopted in this study is that opinion leaders have their subjective attitude in disseminating commodity information, encouraging consumption and purchase, and having a specific emotional colour.

2.2 Management Theories

(1) Mobile internet marketing

The research of opinion leader commodity recommendation on consumers' purchase intention discussed in this study takes the social media in the mobile internet marketing scenario as the starting point, takes the perceived value as the intermediary variable and relationship strength as the regulating variable, and analyzes and studies the impact of the relationship among people, information and commodities in the mobile Internet Environment Community on consumers' purchase intention and purchase behaviour. Mobile internet marketing is the scene of this study, which also enriches the knowledge system of mobile internet marketing.

(2) The SOR model

The SOR model (Stimulus - Organism - Response) is the basis of the research framework of this study. Ivan Pavlov first proposed the classical conditional reflection theory. Then, based on the conditioned reflex experiment, John B. Watson put forward the "stimulus-response learning theory" (also known as "behavioural learning theory"). The stimulus-response theory holds that human behaviour can be divided into stimulus and response; human behaviour is after stimulation. The essence of learning is to form habits, and habits are the process of changing scattered, unorganized and unconditional responses to stimuli into organized and definite conditional responses through learning. Based on behavioural learning theory, Watson explained the model of "stimulus-response" (S-R) for the first time in his dissertation psychology in the eyes of a behaviourist. Watson believes that the stimulation of the external environment leads to the response of human behaviour, so he puts forward the "stimulus-response" model paradigm.

Figure 2-2 The Stimulus-Response Model

Later studies by scholars generally believe that the model paradigm of "S-R" oversimplifies the occurrence process in exploring human psychology. Some scholars believe that the first mock exam should consider the individual's thinking and consciousness. There are some limitations to the S-R model. The stimulus-response theory is too simple, neglecting the human mind's initiative and gradually being replaced by the "Stimulus - Organism - Response" model. Influenced by the above principles, communication effect researchers believe that there is a close consistency between the stimulation of media information and the audience's response. The relationship between them is $S \rightarrow O \rightarrow R$, S can be regarded as information, O as audience and R as the effect.

Figure 2-3 The Stimulus-Organism-Response Model

Gresley emphasizes that stimulation (S) and response (R) simultaneously form proximity conditioned reflex, expressed by the S-R formula. Hull attaches importance to the tendency of the organism (O) to respond between stimulus and response, which is expressed by the S-O-R formula. According to the analysis of this principle, from the perspective of marketers, the marketing activities of enterprises can use this model to analyze the vital factors of buyers' behaviour, such as product, price, sales scene, promotion, opinion leader recommendation and other marketing stimuli. In addition, buyers will also be stimulated by external factors such as economy, technology, politics and culture. All these external stimuli (S) produce consumers' response (R) to purchase behaviour or refusal behaviour or show that they need more information to perceive value and then make measurement and judgment through the benefits balance of consumers' psychological activities (O) series.

Figure 2-4 Marketing Stimulus and Consumer Response Patterns

2.3 Hypotheses

The hypotheses of this study are as follows:

H1: The product information quality recommended by opinion leaders has a significant positive impact on consumers' purchase intention.

H2: The objective expression of opinion leaders has a significant positive impact on consumers' purchase intention.

H3: The intention expression of opinion leaders has a significant positive impact on consumers' purchase intention.

H4a: Perceived value plays a mediating role between the quality of information recommended by opinion leaders and consumers' purchase intention.

H4b: Perceived value plays a mediating role between the objective expression of opinion leaders and consumers' purchase intention.

H4c: Perceived value plays a mediating role between the intentional expression of opinion leaders and consumers' purchase intention.

H5: Relationship strength plays a moderating role between perceived value and consumers' purchase intention.

2.4 Research Framework

According to the Stimulus - Organism - Response (S-O-R) theory, this study takes "stimulus" as the independent variable in the research model, the information presented by leaders' recommended goods. This study takes consumer perceived value and relationship strength as mediators. Finally, this study takes "response" as a dependent variable: consumers' purchase intention. Meanwhile, according to the research hypothesis, the research model of this dissertation quotes the viewpoint of the Stimulus-Response (S-R) theory, that is, the information presented by opinion leaders' commodity recommendation directly stimulates consumers' purchase intention.

Figure 2-5 Research Framework

3. Research instrument and methods

3.1 Questionnaires used in this study

The current dilemma of enterprise mobile internet marketing: After the dividend period of information flow advertising from 2016 to 2018 (low customer acquisition cost, high conversion rate and low production effect requirements), the customer acquisition cost has increased significantly since 2019, the conversion rate has decreased significantly, the production effect requirements have increased, and the operation cost has increased significantly. For enterprises, marketing in the mobile Internet environment needs to change from traffic driven to community relationship-driven. In terms of community operation, opinion leaders are necessary and standard. Whether influential people, organizations, experts, authorities or other forms of existence, an opinion leader is a significant driving force and reason for the community to maintain stickiness. The essence of stickiness is the perceived value of members in the community and the strength of their relationship with opinion leaders. The premise of community existence is to enjoy high-quality products and services, whether actual products or excellent content, which is the foundation. This paper analyzes the impact on consumers when opinion leaders recommend goods in the mobile Internet social media (platform) community, the perceived value as the intermediary variable, and the relationship strength between opinion leaders and consumers in the process of community interaction as the adjustment variable. Analyze and study the impact of the relationship between people and information, people to people, and goods and services on consumers' purchase intention and purchase behaviour in the mobile Internet community. Enriching the mobile internet marketing theory system also has specific practical significance for enterprise marketing in the mobile Internet environment. This paper chooses China's WeChat users, QQ group, WeChat official account, WeChat website, and APP website as the research objects. In addition, China's other social networking APP and overseas Instagram, Facebook and YouTube mobile Internet media are not listed as research objects. In November 2021, an electronic questionnaire was sent to 430 people in Zhejiang, Chongqing, Chengdu, Shanghai and other places. Considering the balance of population distribution, full-time college students, workers in government

organs and institutions, staff managers of enterprises and companies, freelancers and other groups were selected as research samples in terms of occupation.

3.2 Hypotheses

According to the stimulus organism response (S-O-R) theory, this paper takes "stimulus" as the independent variable in the research model, that is, the information presented by the leader's recommendation of goods; Take "organism" as the intermediate variable and regulatory variable, that is, consumer perceived value and relationship strength; Take "response" as a dependent variable, that is, consumers' purchase intention. The information quality presented by opinion leaders of mobile Internet community product recommendation is an essential factor in the shaping product image and corporate brand image, directly affecting consumers' purchase intention. The information itself can be text, pictures, video and audio; the information content can be product concept, function, use-value, corporate culture, business philosophy, etc. This article provides the following hypotheses:

H1 The product information quality recommended by opinion leaders has a significant positive impact on consumers' purchase intention.

H2 The objective expression of opinion leaders has a significant positive impact on consumers' purchase intention.

H3 The intention expression of opinion leaders has a significant positive impact on consumers' purchase intention.

H4 Perceived value is an intermediary between the information quality recommended by opinion leaders and consumers' purchase intention.

H5 Perceived value plays an intermediary role between the objective expression of opinion leaders and consumers' purchase intention.

H6 Perceived value plays an intermediary role between opinion leaders' intentional expression and consumers' purchase intention.

H7 Relationship strength plays a moderating role between perceived value and consumers' purchase intention.

3.3 Selection and content of analysis scale

(i) Variables: Information Quality

On mobile Internet social media, the recommendation information released by opinion leaders is mainly presented to consumers in text, pictures, video, audio and other visual and auditory forms. For different platforms and communities, opinion leaders often guide objective statements or emotional recommendation evaluation after personal trial according to different needs and scenarios, to shorten the distance generated by the network and the endorsement of opinion leaders' credit, reduce consumers' concerns and promote trust in the product or service and themselves. The measurement items of information quality mainly refer to the scales of Dong Yu, Zhou Fei, Ju Xiaolin Puying, etc., to follow up the needs of this study. The details are as follows: Items :

- a. The product information recommended by opinion leaders is professional, accurate, reliable, and has practical value, and the product information disclosure is relatively complete.
- b. The product information recommended by opinion leaders has detailed text description, appropriate pictures and intuitive video and audio explanation
- c. The product or service information recommended by opinion leaders is updated in time and at the forefront of fashion.

(ii) Variables: Objective Expression

Community members receive recommendation information released by opinion leaders on mobile Internet social media. Their attention and interest in further understanding are directly related to the expression of opinion leaders. For different platforms and communities, opinion leaders often reduce consumers' concerns about recommendation interests and motives through objective statements according to different needs and scenarios and promote trust in the product or service and themselves. The measurement items of information quality mainly refer to the scales of Bao Ruixue, Wang Huimin and others, and fine-tune the needs of this study, as follows:

Items:

- a. Opinion leaders objectively describe product quality.
- b. Opinion leaders objectively describe product characteristics.
- c. Opinion leaders did not express their subjective attitude towards products.

(iii) Variable: Intentional Expression

Community members receive recommendation information released by opinion leaders on mobile Internet social media. Their attention and interest in further understanding are directly related to the expression of opinion leaders. For different platforms and communities, opinion leaders often guide emotional recommendation evaluation after personal trial according to different needs and scenarios to shorten the distance generated by the network and the endorsement of opinion leaders' credit, reduce consumers' concerns and promote trust in the product or service and themselves. The measurement items of information quality mainly refer to the scales of Bao Dunan, Bao Ruixue and Wang Huimin, and fine-tune the needs of this study, as follows:

- a. Opinion leaders praise product quality when recommending products.
- b. When recommending products, opinion leaders express their love for products.
- c. Encourage consumers to buy when opinion leaders recommend products.

(iv) Variable: Perceived Value

Chen & Dubinsky (2003) built a model of individually perceived value among consumers to study the significant relationship between the individual perceived value of consumers and their willingness to buy goods. The results show that the perceived value of individual consumers mainly affects their perceived risk and trust and indirectly affects consumers' willingness to buy goods. Therefore, this paper mainly refers to Woodruff's scale to develop the perceived value measurement scale (Woodruff, 2000; Monroe, 2005).

Items:

- a. Make shopping more convenient and fast through the product recommendation of opinion leaders.
- b. Through the product recommendation of opinion leaders, I can save time and improve my shopping efficiency.
- c. The products and services recommended by opinion leaders are value for money.
- d. The community has a good shopping experience through the product recommendation of opinion leaders.

(v) Variables: Relationship Strength

Relationship strength refers to the familiarity between the information receiver and the recommender. Frenzen (1990) summarized the relationship strength into four aspects: familiarity, intimacy, support, and similarity when studying consumer purchase behaviour. Chang Yaping (2010) appropriately adjusted the measurement scale of a related degree combined with China's network development. Based on the research of Frenzen and Chang

Yaping, this study also reflects the strength of mobile social media user relationships in the above four aspects. The specific measurement scales are as follows:

Items:

- a. In mobile social media, I often pay attention to the daily dynamics of opinion leaders.
- b. In real life, I am familiar with the recommender.
- c. On this platform, I often discuss personal topics with the recommender.
- d. The recommender and I have similar backgrounds (interests, hobbies, education, etc.).

(vi) Variable: Purchase Intention

This study refers to the scale developed by Dodds (1991) and Gefen and Straub (2004) and the scale developed by Pavlov and Fygenson (2006). Combined with the actual situation of this study, the author appropriately modifies the above measurement scale as follows:

Items:

- a. Through the product information recommended by the opinion leader, I agree with this product, and I will buy the goods and services.
- b. The product information recommended by the opinion leader has provided great help for my purchase decision. I will consider purchasing the goods and services.
- c. Through the product information recommended by opinion leaders, I prefer to buy this product.

The questionnaire design of this study adopts the format of a 5-level Likert scale, "1" stands for strongly disagree, "2" stands for disagree, "3" stands for moderate, "4" stands for agree and "5" stands for strongly agree. The internal consistency coefficient of the information quality scale is 0.920; The internal consistency coefficient of the objective expression scale was 0.859; The internal consistency coefficient of intention expression scale was 0.917; The internal consistency coefficient of perceived value scale was 0.927; The internal consistency coefficient of the relationship strength scale was 0.911; The internal consistency coefficient of purchase intention scale was 0.916; The consistency coefficients of the above items are more significant than 0.8, and the reliability of all scales is high.

3.4 Data analysis methods

The effective questionnaire was statistically tested in this study using the process plug-in of Amos 22.0 software and SPSS software. The data analysis of this study uses a variety of data processing methods to verify the reliability of the hypothesis, such as descriptive statistical analysis, correlation analysis, discriminant validity, facet convergence validity and combination reliability, internal consistency test of the scale, hierarchical regression and multiple regression results of the model. The above technical means test the scientificity and rationality of the research framework provided by this study to obtain objective and accurate results.

4. Analysis of questionnaire survey results

4.1 Analysis of the quality of opinion leaders' recommendation information and consumers' buying intention

The results of multiple regression of the model are given by hierarchical regression. Model 1 has control variables, and model 2 adds independent variables based on control variables. According to the adjusted R², the model design is reasonable. At the same time, the F value is significant, and the Vif value of each variable is less than 10, indicating that there is no severe multicollinearity problem in the regression equation. According to the regression results, opinion leaders' recommendation information quality ($\beta=0.632$, $p<0.001$) has a significant positive impact on consumers' purchase intention, and H1 is supported.

Table 1 Regression Results of H1

Variable	Model1	Model2
Dependent variable: consumer purchase intention		
Gender	-0.199	-0.096
Age	0.101	0.106*
Education	-0.017	-0.008
Number of purchases	0.204**	0.056
Quality of information recommended by opinion leaders		0.632***
Constant	3.122	0.955
Adjust R2	0.043	0.393
F	2.951*	23.414***

Note: * P < 0.05, ** P < 0.01, *** P < 0.001

4.2 Analysis of opinion leaders' objective expression and consumers' purchasing intentions

According to the regression results, the objective expression of opinion leaders ($\beta=0.641$, $p<0.001$) has a significant positive impact on consumers' purchase intention, and H2 is supported.

Table 2 Regression Results of H2

Variable	Model1	Model3
Dependent variable: consumer purchase intention		
Gender	-0.199	-0.020
Age	0.101	0.051
Education	-0.017	0.039
Number of purchases	0.204**	0.089
Objective expression of opinion leaders		0.641***
Constant	3.122	0.939
Adjust R2	0.043	0.414
F	2.951*	25.420***

Note: * P < 0.05, ** P < 0.01, *** P < 0.001

4.3 Analysis of opinion leaders' intention expression and consumers' purchase intention

According to the regression results, the opinion leader's intention expression ($\beta=0.567$, $p<0.001$) has a significant positive effect on consumers' purchase intention, and H3 is supported.

Table 3 Regression Results of H3

Variable	Model1	Model4
Dependent variable: consumer purchase intention		
Gender	-0.199	-0.173
Age	0.101	0.117*
Education	-0.017	-0.009
Number of purchases	0.204**	0.058
Opinion leaders' intentional expression		0.567***
Constant	3.122	1.139
Adjust R2	0.043	0.321
F	2.951*	70.101**

Note: * P < 0.05, ** P < 0.01, *** P < 0.001

4.4 Analysis of perceived value on information quality and consumer purchase intention

This study used the process plug-in of SPSS software to test the mediation effect. The bootstrap sample size was 5000, and the confidence interval was 95%. According to the regression results, the direct effect of opinion leaders' recommendation information quality on

consumers' purchase intention is not significant($\beta=0.024$, the confidence interval is [-0.124, 0.172] including 0), and the indirect effect is significant($\beta=0.607$, the confidence interval is [0.457, 0.786] excluding 0). Therefore, perceived value plays a completely intermediary role between opinion leaders' information quality and consumers' purchase intention.

Table 4 Bootstrap Test Results of Perceived Value Mediation

Items	Effect	SD	95% Confidence interval		
			Lower limits	Upper limit	
Perceived value	Indirect effect	0.607	0.082	0.457	0.786
	Direct effect	0.024	0.075	-0.124	0.172

4.5 Analysis of perceived value on objective expression and consumer purchase intention

According to the regression results, the direct effect of opinion leaders' objective expression on consumers' purchase intention is not significant ($\beta=0.078$, the confidence interval is [-0.065, 0.222] contains 0), and the indirect effect is significant ($\beta=0.563$, the confidence interval is [0.424, 0.747] does not contain 0). Therefore, perceived value plays a complete intermediary role between the objective expression of opinion leaders and consumers' purchase intention.

Table 5 Bootstrap Test Results of Perceived Value Mediation

Items	Effect	SD	95% Confidence interval		
			Lower limits	Upper limit	
Perceived value	Indirect effect	0.563	0.083	0.424	0.747
	Direct effect	0.078	0.073	-0.065	0.222

4.6 Analysis of perceived value on intentional expression and consumer purchase intention

According to the regression results, the direct effect of opinion leaders' intentional expression on consumers' purchase intention is not significant($\beta=0.084$, the confidence interval is [-0.041, 0.208] contains 0), and the indirect effect is significant($\beta=0.484$, the confidence interval is [0.356, 0.642] excluding 0). Therefore, perceived value plays a complete intermediary role between opinion leaders' intentional expression and consumers' purchase intention.

Table 6 Bootstrap Test Results of Perceived Value Mediation

Items	Effect	SD	95% Confidence interval		
			Lower limits	Upper limit	
Perceived value	Indirect effect	0.484	0.073	0.356	0.642
	Direct effect	0.084	0.063	-0.041	0.208

4.7 Analysis of relationship strength on perceived value and consumer purchase intention

The hypothesis of regulatory effect was verified by hierarchical regression analysis. The regression analysis results are shown in the table below. Although it can be seen from model 3 that the interaction between perceived value and relationship strength after standardization has no significant impact on consumers' purchase intention ($\beta=-0.023$, $P=0.631 > 0.05$), the data results do not support the hypothesis.

Table 7 Hierarchical Regression Test Moderating Effect

Variable	Purchase intention					
	M1		M2		M3	
	Std. Coefficients	P value	Std. Coefficients	P value	Std. Coefficients	P value
Gender	-0.122	0.110	-0.053	0.252	-0.056	0.232
Age	0.120	0.112	0.042	0.359	0.041	0.370
Education	-0.018	0.812	0.120*	0.015	0.118*	0.018
Number of purchases	0.210**	0.006	0.014	0.763	0.016	0.741
Perceived value			0.679***	0.000	0.674***	0.000
Relationship strength			0.183**	0.006	0.192**	0.006
Perceived value x Relationship strength					-0.023	0.631
R ²	0.065		0.666		0.667	
ΔR ²	0.065		0.601		0.000	
F	2.951*	0.022	55.519***	0.000	47.402***	0.000

Note: * P < 0.05, ** P < 0.01, *** P < 0.001

5. Conclusions and Implications

5.1 Conclusion

Based on how the presentation of product recommendation information of opinion leaders in the mobile social media community affects consumers' purchase intention and purchase behaviour, this study focuses on the following issues: 1. What impact does product information quality, intentional expression, and objective expression recommended by opinion leaders of the mobile Internet community have on consumers' purchase intention? 2. What role does consumers' perceived value play in information quality, objective expression, intention expression and purchase intention? 3. What role does the relationship strength between opinion leaders and consumers play between perceived value and purchase intention? This paper mainly uses the literature research method and questionnaire survey method for analysis and research. The respondents' age, occupation, and region are evenly distributed as far as possible. Three hundred sixty-five questionnaires are collected and analyzed through the process plug-in of Amos 22.0 software and SPSS software. The conclusions are as follows: the quality of opinion leaders' recommendation information significantly impacts consumers' purchase intention. The objective expression of opinion leaders has a significant positive impact on consumers' purchase intention. The intention expression of opinion leaders has a significant positive impact on consumers' purchase intention. Perceived value plays a complete intermediary role between information quality and consumers' purchase intention. Perceived value plays a complete intermediary role between objective expression and consumers' purchase intention. Perceived value plays a complete intermediary role between intentional expression and consumers' purchase intention. Relationship strength has no moderating effect between perceived value and consumers' purchase intention.

5.2 Implications

In marketing, language strategy identifies and distinguishes different marketing scenarios and then selects the appropriate language style expression to affect consumers' behaviour effectively. An effective marketing language strategy in the mobile Internet community is critical in improving consumers' attitudes towards opinion leaders' products. The language characteristics of objective expression and intention expression adopted by opinion leaders in recommending products affect consumers' feelings and purchase intention in different scenarios. According to the regression results, the intention expression of opinion leaders has a significant positive impact on consumers' purchase intention, the objective expression of opinion leaders has a significant positive impact on consumers' purchase intention, and the objective intention expression has a significant impact on consumers' purchase intention,

indicating that the characteristics of opinion leaders are essential; In the era of incremental economy, the value of personal IP has not been fully demonstrated, but in this era of stock economy, brand value will be reflected, and that is the logic behind opinion leaders. It is just like the Internet Protocol IP. Everyone is a product. Build yourself as the best product in your life. A personal brand is the best moat. Once created, it is difficult to be copied.

One of the functions of the mobile Internet community is to reduce the trust cost to reduce the marketing cost of enterprises. The three essential elements of community operation are trust, reciprocity and community emotion. The community cannot be established just for the rapid realization of sales products. The community is mainly used to deepen the relationship strength between enterprises and users and improve users' value perception. The strengthening of community emotion and relationships is a long-term and continuous interaction, including online and offline. Enlightenment from the intermediary role of perceived value: according to the formula of perceived value, consumers' perceived commodity value is the benefits they can obtain minus the costs they need to pay. There are two ways to improve the perceived value and enhance consumers' purchase intention. The first is to reduce consumers' payment costs. If more than two enterprises adopt this way, it is possible to form a price war. The low price strategy is suitable for enterprises with large-scale production and sales conditions to attract traffic in the short term or with few products. However, the appropriate time and space are very effective and unsuitable for most small, medium-sized and micro-enterprises. The second is to improve consumers' benefits, and consumers can obtain more benefits from businesses. Sometimes businesses will increase their costs, resulting in a decline in profits, but sometimes they do not need businesses to increase costs, or the increased costs can be ignored. Sometimes they can be offset by cost conversion. In any case, consumers can perceive the improvement of benefits and promote their purchase intention. From the perspective of enterprises, the dimensions that can improve consumers' perceived value include the information quality presented by-products, the value shaping formed by language strategies in various links of communication with users, relationship strength, added value: such as credit, free delivery, guarantee, installation, after-sales service, etc., as well as corporate social responsibility information: the responsibility of enterprises to consumers, communities and the environment.

For enterprises and individuals engaged in commercial activities, the fundamental existence is that the products or services provided can bring value to consumers. Therefore, solving people's needs is the basis for the value and development of enterprises and individuals engaged in commercial activities. It can also be seen from the results of this data analysis that the direct effect of consumers' perceived value, opinion leaders, information quality, objective expression and intentional expression on consumers' purchase intention is not significant, but the indirect effect is significant. From another perspective, community operation and the organizational activities of opinion leaders also increase consumers' perceived value. Based on the principles of humanization, personalization and diversification, enterprises build products around users' needs, carry out marketing activities around users' interests, and operate the community around users' emotional needs.

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